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The contributions of Gilberto Freyre for the acculturation research

Abstract

This paper aims to report the contribution of the Gilberto Freyre theory for the acculturation research. The Gilberto Freyre theory provides an emic point of view, which is rooted in the Brazilian culture. The Gilberto Freyre description of the Brazilian culture emphasized acculturation as a reciprocal learning and as a motivated phenomenon. He also reported a two-way of cultural influences and changes, in which a European majority is reported to learn with the oppressed minorities. The historical backgrounds are conditioning the reactions regarding the cultural changes, and the backgrounds are also conditioning the different approaches regarding the acculturation phenomenon. Regardless the advantages of the Gilberto Freyre theoretical rationale, it must be a target of a critical point of view, because it was placed in a social dominance point of view, which started with the Portuguese conquest of Ceuta.

Resumo

Este artigo tem como objetivo reportar a contribuição da teoria de Gilberto Freyre para a investigação acerca da aculturação. A obra maior de Gilberto Freyre é capaz de reportar um ponto de vista emic, o qual está enraizado na cultura brasileira. A descrição de Gilberto Freyre acerca da cultura brasileira enfatizou a aculturação como uma aprendizagem recíproca e como um fenómeno motivado. Ele também reportou dois sentidos de influências e de mudanças culturais, em que uma maioria europeia é reportada estar a aprender com as minorias oprimidas. Os *backgrounds* históricos estão a condicionar as reações face às mudanças culturais, e os *backgrounds* culturais também estão a condicionar as diferentes abordagens acerca do fenómeno da aculturação. Apesar das vantagens do racional teórico de Gilberto Freyre, este deve ser alvo dum ponto de vista crítico, uma vez que este assenta num ponto de vista de domínio social, o qual começou com a conquista de Ceuta.

1. The definition of the acculturation concept

The acculturation phenomenon is defined by its main dimensions: the intercultural contact, the mutual interactions among different cultures (Bourhis, Moise, Perreault, & Senécal, 1997; Redfield, Linton, & Herskovits, 1936), by learning a second culture (Powell, 1880; Rudmin, 2009), and by cultural changes at individual (Graves, 1967), and at collective levels (Malinowski, 1958). In the definition of the acculturation construct it is

important to take into account that cultural changes can drive to the reinterpretation of the cultural legacy (Barth, 1969), because acculturation is a dynamic process of cultural creation (Boas, 1982; Malinowski, 1958). It is also important to take into account that acculturation is regulated by motivations, and it is often antagonistic and asymmetric.

2. The main models to approach the acculturation phenomenon

Arends-Tóth and Van de Vijver (2006) stated that the acculturation topic has three models; the assimilation, the multicultural and the fusion. Castro (2012, 2014a, 2015) added the intercultural model, which is supposed to be related to the Francophone cultural legacy (Taylor, 2012).

The main features from the acculturation models will be described. However, it is necessary to cast light over a theoretical detail. The words majority and minority are applied in the current paper, because they are employed in the Anglo-Saxon literature. At the international level, it is needed to standardize the concepts, regardless that they can be targets of critics. The more accurate words would be the dominant and the dominated cultural groups, when the research is placed or it is concerned with asymmetric power relationships.

On the current article it also necessary to state that the labels Anglo-Saxon and Lusophone are not essentializing entire cultures or countries. The current paper aimed to be Emic. The word Emic and its definition were coined by Pike (1954):

. . . the *ETIC* . . . , an author is primarily concerned with generalized statements about the data . . . classifies systematically all comparable data, . . . of all cultures in the world, into a single system . . . an *EMIC* one is in essence valid for only one language (or one culture) at a time or . . . it is an attempt to discover, and to describe the pattern of that particular language or culture . . . rather than an attempt to describe them in reference to a generalized classification . . . (p. 8).

On the present article it was not a goal to produce generalizations, and as Brislin wrote the Emic approach aims to establish: “. . . valid principles that describe behavior in any one culture under study, taking into account what people themselves value as meaningful and important.” (1976, p. 217). This article stresses a comparative approach,

mainly regarding the Anglo-Saxon culture. It compares the Anglo-Saxon and two Lusophones countries (Brazil and in a lesser degree Portugal), and it searches more for differences than for cultural similarities. However, when researchers are working with large ethnic labels, such as Anglo-Saxon, Anglo-American, Lusophone or Francophone, they have the tendency to forget internal diversity. Yet, USA has internal diversity. Canada has Quebec, i.e., a major and relevant Francophone cultural group, besides the indigenous cultures. And the Anglo-Saxons cultures have differences, e.g., USA, Canada, and Australia have different historical backgrounds, and they have different immigration policies. Furthermore, USA, Canada, and Brazil were colonies, and they were and they are still immigrants receiving countries. Immigration expanded their internal cultural diversities, besides their previous and pervasive European groups, and their Indigenous and African-American cultures. However, from a comparative point of view, there is a Lusophone, a Francophone and an Anglo-Saxon culture, regardless their internal diversities and the diversity among countries and even their regions.

On Cross-Cultural Psychology, often, labels as Hispanics, Latinos or Asians are forgetting internal diversities, and those large labels are also confounding different countries and very different historical and cultural backgrounds (Rudmin, Wang, Castro, 2016). In the USA or in Canada Hispanics or Asians are belonging to very different countries and historical backgrounds, e.g., Chile, Spain, Mexico, Japan, India or China. However, it is not the case of the current article. Besides, on the current article, the Anglo-Saxon and the Lusophone cultures (Brazil and Portugal) are not under an asymmetric power relationship. Therefore, there is no possibility of stigmatization, discrimination, and reproduction of social status. Another argument to stress is that such large labels are placed on the fact that the Anglo-Saxon culture is, today, the pervasive culture, which includes the academic production and point of view, allowing a comparative approach.

According to Castro (2014a, b), on the assimilation model, the minority culture is expected to disappear, after to be completely adapted to the majority culture. The mutual learning will not be reported on the expected outcome, because the minority will be completely assimilated into the majority culture. The European assimilation policies, during

the 19th century, and the Chicago School conceptualization (Gordon, 1964; Park, 1928) are examples of the assimilation model.

On the multicultural model, the minority culture is expected to get cultural adaptation, maintaining, however at the same time its own culture (Berry, 2001). On the multicultural model, just the minority is learning, and both cultures are only interacting on the larger society. It is important to notice that the larger society may not imply the segregation of the minority group, but rather a minimal intercultural interaction, which is backed by the majority culture. The WASP culture (White, Anglo-Saxon and Protestant), and the Berry Model (2001) are examples of the multicultural approach.

On the fusion model there is interaction, and mutual learning among the different cultures, and there are still cultural mixtures (Herskovits, 1938; Simons, 1901), which will produce a new culture (LaFromboise, Coleman, & Gerton, 1998) with internal diversity (Bastide, 1971; Castro, 2012, 2014a, b), because the different cultures are adding new cultural features to each other. The Brazilian and the Russian cultures are examples of the fusion model. The Russian culture is close to the Brazilian one, even because both are often implying fusion under asymmetric power relationships (Simons, 1901c). The Freyre (1986; Rudmin, et al., 2016) and the Ortiz (1995) theories, or the policies of Alexander the Great (Simons, 1901a, b) are also examples of the fusion model.

On the intercultural model at private and at individual levels the minority can change or can maintain its cultural legacy, being applied the laissez-faire point of view at those domains. The minority at public level is expected to get cultural adaptation regarding the majority culture, for instance, at labor, and at educational domains. However, at the institutional level, the interaction among different cultures is reduced. The universalistic values from the French Republic can be an example of the model, because those institutional values are not expected to change, due to the minority agency. Taylor (2012) stressed that the intercultural model of Quebec appeared as a reaction regarding the Anglo-Saxon multicultural model. According to Taylor (2012), the intercultural model implied

interaction among the different cultures living in the same space, but the multicultural did not.

3. Gilberto Freyre

Gilberto Freyre (Recife, 1900-1987) was a Brazilian sociologist and anthropologist. He was educated in Brazil and in the United States of America at the Baylor University, and still at the Columbia University with Franz Boas. In 1933, Freyre wrote *The Master and the Slaves* (Freyre, 1986), stressing a comparison among the Portuguese colonization in Brazil with other European settlements; mainly the Anglo-Saxon. The Anglo-Saxon culture, in the Freyre's words, was doing substitution, and it was not doing cultural adaptation regarding the oppressed cultures: ". . . social engineering completed by the art of merely political transaction – in which the English have revealed themselves masters – but not of cultural transaction." (Freyre, 1961, p. 57). Therefore, according to Freyre, the Anglo-Saxons were not doing cultural adaptation regarding other cultures, but they were just assimilating them: ". . . from a sociological point of view . . . the selection should be only in one direction. (Freyre, 1961, p. 58). Yet, according to Freyre, in Brazil, the Portuguese adaptation resulted in a culture of fusion. Hence, the Brazilian culture was done by a two-way of cultural influences, and the Portuguese ruling culture was reporting to learn with the oppressed cultures. Moreover, Freyre stated that no culture is superior to another, stressing another feature of the fusion model (LaFromboise, et al., 1998).

3.1 The Freyre legacy

Freyre thought that the Portuguese people were more tolerant, and more able to acquire cultural adaptation at three levels; cultural, ecological, and biological. According to Freyre, the Portuguese culture rendered to a social harmony under the Portuguese paternalist and agrarian powers in the North of Brazil: ". . . by intimate living together with native people . . ." (Freyre, 1961, p. 39). The biological adaptation occurred by "intermarriages" between the ruling European males and the oppressed females; the indigenous and the Africans. Hence, the Brazilian culture of fusion occurred under an

antagonistic and an asymmetric relationship among cultures and genders. The “intermarriage” topic needs a note. The painter Modesto Brocos on the famous *A Redenção de Cam* displays a white male with his half-breed African-Brazilian female, their half-breed son, and the presumed African-Brazilian grandmother. The work displays at the same time the racial whitening theory, because the son is whiter than the mother, and he is even whiter than the grandmother. However, it also displays the female agency in order to get upward social mobility. It is also necessary to note that often “intermarriage” was made by the force or not by matrimony. Therefore, “intermarriage” is not the accurate word. However, it is applied on the anthropological, the sociological and on the psychological literature.

3.2 Freyre as a consensual ideology

In the 50s, Freyre traveled to the Portuguese colonies, enlarging his theory towards the Portuguese Empire, and he called it of Luso-Tropicalism: "Diverse expressions of a single symbiotic culture that can be called Lusotropical culture" (Freyre, 1961, p. 57). After the 50s, Freyre was fostered by the Portuguese dictatorship. The Portuguese ruler group started to look at the African colonies and at Goa (India), taking into account the Brazilian case as a “successful” example. Yet, nowadays the stereotype about the Portuguese plasticity prevails even under a democratic political system:

All of those elements are to be found in the representations of Portuguese identity before and after Freyre. One can find them in Portuguese social sciences and literature, in official discourses, and in commonsense identity self-representations with amazing resilience and capacity to adapt to different political situations. (Almeida, 2004, p. 48)

According to Araújo and Maeso (2010), the consensus ideology about the Luso-Tropical culture is still working on the current schoolbooks. Therefore, the Luso-Tropical theory would survive in the future generations, as Cabecinhas (2010), and Cabecinhas and Feijó (2010), and still Vala, Lopes and Lima, (2008) have pointed out.

4. The Freyre legacy for the acculturation approach

According to Castro (2014a), the work of Freyre (1986) is grounded in three main features. The first feature is the presumed Portuguese plasticity in order to learn second cultures. The Portuguese people are presumed to be more able to get cultural adaptation, and they are also presumed to be more tolerant than other European cultures. Castro (2014a) has criticized this point of view, because it implies asymmetric power relationships among a European culture, regarding the non-Europeans cultures. As Freyre (1986) himself reported in the *The Master and the Slaves*, the cultural mixtures are not avoiding the intercultural violence, (and the violence between genders). According to Castro (2014a), the Brazilian culture is not a harmonious culture, and any emergent culture would devise a new ethnic identity (Barth, 1969), which can establish new conflicts with other cultural groups.

Regardless that the Brazilian culture is more mixed than the Anglo-Saxon North American culture, what was underlying the Freyre comparison between the Portuguese and the Anglo-Saxon colonization, was the social dominance point of view (Sidanius, & Pratto, 1999) among the European vis-à-vis the non-European cultures. According to Dupront (1997), the crusades are the precursors of the European colonialism. The crusades, as the conquest of Ceuta, in 1415, are implying a violent approach and a social dominance point of view, which is ethnocentric and Eurocentric (Goody, 2006). Besides the social dominance point of view, because Freyre was fostered by the Portuguese dictatorship, in order to vindicate the Portuguese oppressive power, the ambiguous meaning of the Freyre theory remains until today. In order to avoid the ambiguous meaning, the current researcher is just interested in the main work of Freyre; *The Masters and the Slaves*.

Regardless the Castro (2014a) critical point of view, the Freyre work remains an objective and observable reality in the Brazilian society. For instance, in the United States of America the level of “intermarriages” is low (Batson, Qian, & Lichter, 2006; Qian, & Lichter, 2007). Yet, in Brazil, the miscegenation is a sociological reality (Bastide, 1973; Braudel, 1943; Cardoso, 2003; Herskovits, 1967; Holanda, 1998; Nabuco, 1908; Ribeiro, 1995; Veríssimo, 1887). Although, it is important to state that the mixtures of cultures are not a solution by themselves for the intercultural conflicts (Lévi-Strauss, 1986).

The second main feature is grounded in the fact that Freyre reported a two-way process of cultural influences; he was reporting the cultural influences from the oppressed minorities, and he was also reporting that the European dominant culture was learning with the non-European cultures. The “intermarriages” are implying the biological mixtures among the races, and also a double education, in which enculturation and acculturation are working together. In the Portuguese language, the book *The Master and the Slaves* (Freyre, 1986) is called *Casa-Grande e Senzala*. The *Casa-Grande* is the European house, and the *Senzala* is the place for the slaves. As a former president of Brazil wrote, the Europeans and the Slaves were living in the same space (Cardoso, 2003). Therefore, it encompassed a multicultural dimension, because different cultures were living in the same territory (Schalk-Soekar, & Van de Vijver, 2008). However, it implies mutual interaction, cultural mixtures and to report them into the majority culture. Besides, the emerging culture is allowing the existence of cultural diversity. For instance, the Candomblé and the Umbanda religions are representing different mixtures, but both are the results of acculturation (Bastide, 1971). As Serres (1991) wrote, in Brazil the different cultures are living together, they are mixed, and the mutual learning is reported. Besides the cultural diversity, it is necessary to stress that the religion cultural domain reports also the African-Brazilian agency. Herskovits (1967) reported how the African-Americans were not in a passive position regarding the European rulers. Afterward, Bastide reported the African-Brazilian agency, because they achieved a mixed religion (1971).

The third main feature is that Freyre perceived the intercultural relationship mediated by learning a second culture. However, it was regulated by strong motivations. Hence, he was reporting a two-way process of intercultural influences, but the relationship was antagonistic and asymmetric. In the European Francophone culture, the word acculturation was dismissed, because it is supposedly related with the colonial times (Brégent, Mokoukolo, & Pasquier, 2008; Sabatier, & Boutry, 2006). Castro (2014a, 2016c) did a systematic review in the Portuguese literature about the emigration and the immigration phenomena, and the word acculturation rarely appeared. However, the word acculturation was common during the Portuguese Empire (Castro, 2014a). Rudmin, Wang

and Castro (2016) have stated that the word acculturation is still connected with the colonial times. However, as Freyre (1986) have displayed, it is possible to report an acculturation process with two-ways of intercultural influences, even when it is regulated by strong motivations.

Today, the world is facing climate changes (Lovelock, 1972), an increase in the intercultural contacts, faster migrations, and faster cultural changes. The world is interdependent (i.e. at economic and at cultural domains), it has several main cultural centers (i.e. China, India, USA, Brazil, Russia, Central Asia, and Japan). There is an increase of the available information (Serres, 2012; Stiegler, 2015), and there are easier and faster communications (Hobsbawm, 1995), and finally the ethnic identities are intertwined (Serres, 2012). Today, the ethnic identity is formulated beyond the tribe, the family, and the State in an individualistic and complex way (Bauman, 2004; Lyotard, 1988).

In the material, the ecological and the technological conditions described above, acculturation, as learning a second culture, is working at the same time with enculturation and with socialization, and the different cultures are sharing cultural features (Castro, 2016c Kramer, 2012), which can trigger constant and new intercultural conflicts. Often, maintenance is working at the same time with cultural change. Researchers must place the emphasis on what is common to human beings, thus on learning (Lévi-Strauss, 1986).

The Berry Model is today the pervasive model on Cross-Cultural Psychology. The Model works by the dimensions of contact and cultural maintenance. The main feature of the Berry Model is to provide importance for the minority cultural maintenance. The latter is its main historical contribution, mainly regarding the forced assimilation. However, the Berry Model holds cultural interaction, which is stressed by the Québécoise intercultural model (Taylor, 2012). The Berry Model is devised in a way that cultures are not expected to share cultural traits (Bowskill, Lyons & Coyle, 2007; Castro, 2014a, b, 2015, 2016a, b, c; Rudmin, 2003). The Berry Model is working well for recent immigrants and refugees, because cultures are not sharing cultural features. However, it is working barely for minorities who are living with the majority for generations, because minorities are already

acculturated. Hence, majority and minority are sharing cultural traits (Castro, 2014a, 2015, 2016a, b, c), and the model does not work well under that condition.

The majority of the Psychological works about acculturation are neglecting the majority preferences or attitudes, apart from the works of Rudmin, Villemo and Olsen (2007), Geschke, Mummendey, Kessler and Funke (2010), and Castro (2014a, b, 2015, 2016a). The pervasive literature is not displaying two-way of cultural influences, and it is not approaching acculturation as learning (Castro, 2016b: Rudmin, 2009). Furthermore, intercultural contact leads to cultural change, and not to the maintenance of the minority culture (Castro, 2015). The intercultural contact also leads to changes in the dominant culture. Yet, the position of the majority culture is neglected by the Berry Model.

Another interesting model is the Bourhis et al. (1997) Interactive Acculturation Model (IAM), and an even more interesting model is the Navas et al. (2005) Relative Acculturation Extended Model, because it approaches acculturation between its real and ideal dimensions. As Touraine (2007) wrote: “The absolute multiculturalist hypothesis is as absurd as that of the cultural homogeneity of a city or country. Intercultural relations are the only reality - and they are what need to be studied, from trampling over the other to cultural mixing.” (p. 153).

5. Conclusion and suggestions

The Freyre’s work is still attractive for researchers (Bastos, 1998, 2012; Meucci, 2005; Soares, 2002; Velho, 2008). The Freyre’s work (1986) is useful to display that it is necessary to take into account the historical backgrounds, in order to understand the acculturation phenomenon and research. The Portuguese historical background is different regarding the Anglo-Saxon one. The Portuguese historical legacy is done by mutual interaction, by reporting to learn with other cultures, and by praising the fusion of cultures. The Anglo-Saxon culture is done by the minimal interaction (Bastide, 1973; Myrdal, 1944; Todd, 1994) among the different cultures, and it does not report to learn with other cultures. Besides, the Anglo-Saxon culture is praising the cultural maintenance of the minorities (but, it is also implying the majority Anglo-Saxon cultural maintenance):

The Englishman, on the contrary, continuing obstinately attached to the customs and the most insignificant habits of his forefathers, has remained in the midst of the American solitudes just what he was in the bosom of European cities; he would not allow of any communication with savages whom he despised, and avoided with care the union of his race with theirs. Thus while the French exercised no salutary influence over the Indians, the English have always remained alien from them. (Tocqueville, 2002, p. 379).

In the western cultures, it is necessary to devise theoretical rationales, besides the Anglo-Saxon culture. It is necessary to devise research designs with two-ways of cultural influences, displaying the majority concerns about its cultural changes, besides the minority appraisals (Castro, 2015). It is necessary an interdisciplinary point of view, and to employ the mixed method (Ozer, 2013), because the acculturation phenomenon is complex (Morin, 2003), and it is even relative (Navas, et al., 2005). Finally, it is also necessary to approach acculturation as a learning phenomenon, which is regulated by strong motivations. The research emphasis must be placed on how people is learning; getting information, instruction, imitation, and mentoring (Rudmin, 2009), and still the rational disputation or arguing, curiosity, observation, listening, reading, travelling, and the use of internet as ways to learn a second culture (Castro, 2014a; b, Castro, 2016b). Regarding the motivations, the researcher must take into account the gains and the losses from the social practices, and not only the cultural attitudes. The look must be close the anthropological regard (Lévi-Strauss, 1986), thus a distant one, even because what is common and similar between the Anglo-Saxon and the Portuguese cultures is the violence and the social dominance point of view regarding other cultures. However, both cultures have different approaches regarding the intercultural contact. Instead the social dominance point of view, it is necessary a soft power approach (Nye, 2011). Freyre reported how the individuals are learning a second culture, and the associated motivations. He approached topics which are inner to Psychology; learning and motivation. Hence, Psychology is able to approach the acculturation phenomenon. The article displays how a European ruler group reports to interact, to learn and to mix cultural traits with dominated cultures. The ultimate goal of the article was to report a two-way of intercultural learning. Yet, as a research limitation and suggestion, it is also necessary to highlight that the dominated cultures have an active position and agency. As Freyre (1986) achieved, it is needed to provide a positive value to the African-American and to the Indigenous cultures.

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